

STRUCTURE / PROPERTIES CORRELATIONS IN CAST
SILICON CARBIDE / ALUMINUM 2014 COMPOSITE

A.H. Esmaili¹, K.K. Chawla¹, A.K. Datye², A.K. Vasudevan³, AND Q. Mei²

¹New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology, Socorro, NM 87801,

²University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, NM 87131,

³Office of Naval Research, Arlington, VA 22217

ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to characterize the aging behavior of the cast SiC particle/aluminum 2014 composite and Al 2014 at different temperatures. The aging characteristics of the Al 2014 matrix and the unreinforced alloy were monitored with a 0.25 N load Vickers hardness test at various aging temperatures. The difference in time to peak age between the Al 2014 matrix and the unreinforced alloy as a function of aging time decreased as the aging temperature decreased from 195 °C to 150 °C. The large difference in the peak aging time observed at higher aging temperatures is attributed to the relatively large difference between thermal expansion coefficient of aluminum and silicon carbide which results in substantial thermal stresses leading to dislocation generation at the matrix/particle interface region. The high dislocation density provided sites for heterogeneous nucleation and growth of S' precipitates resulting in accelerated aging kinetics in the matrix. At lower aging temperatures the importance of dislocations as sites for nucleation of the precipitates was reduced since homogeneous nucleation is easier, consequently, the differences between the matrix and the unreinforced alloy were small. Differential scanning calorimetry confirmed the presence of GP zones and S' precipitates at 150 °C and only S' precipitates at 195 °C. Thus, the aging kinetics of the Al 2014 matrix differed markedly with the aging temperature because of the competition between homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic particles, when added to a metal alloy, markedly increase the dislocation density in the matrix upon cooling from the solutionizing temperature [1]. The increase in dislocation density is mostly due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the particle and the matrix. Chawla and Metzger [2] in a study of tungsten fiber reinforced single crystal copper matrix composites, used etch pitting technique to observe these dislocations. They identified the importance of thermal stresses and the consequent altered microstructure of the matrix. The dislocation density was the highest at the W/Cu interface and decreased with increasing distance from the interface into the matrix. It was concluded that the higher

dislocation densities were caused by the difference (4:1) ratio in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of Cu and W in the non-precipitation hardenable W/Cu system. Arsenaault and Fisher [3], using transmission electron microscopy, observed a high density of dislocations ($4 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^{-2}$) clustered around the ends of SiC whiskers (SiC_w) and forming low angle cell boundaries in a 20% SiC_w/Al 6061 composite. They also observed very fine precipitates along the dislocations. Subsequently, they made in-situ observation of dislocations generated due to thermal mismatch using a hot stage in a high voltage transmission electron microscopy [4]. These dislocations form heterogeneous nucleation sites for the precipitates in the matrix during subsequent aging treatments. This in turn results in the alteration of the precipitation kinetics in the matrix of the composite as compared to the unreinforced material [5–10].

The effect of other types of ceramic particles such as B_4C , SiC, etc. on the matrix microstructure has been the subject of several investigations [7,8–10]. Nieh and Karlak [8] found that the Al 6061 matrix containing B_4C particles reached a peak hardness in 3 hours at 177 °C while a control alloy took 10 hours. Christman et al. [9] in their TEM study of SiC_w/Al composite observed the nucleation of second phase precipitates on dislocations and growth along [001] directions. These authors observed S' nucleation after less than 1h of aging at 177 °C. In the case of control Al alloys it took almost 4h of aging at the same temperature before any S' could be detected. Also, Suresh et al. [5] found the peak aging time for the matrix of SiC_p/Al 3.5 weight % Cu, made by casting route, to be around 16–24 hours at 190 °C, while that of the unreinforced alloy was around 60 hours. Investigators in all these studies attributed this acceleration in the aging kinetics to the presence of high diffusivity paths along the dislocations introduced by differential thermal expansion at the particle/matrix interfaces. Consequently, the presence of these dislocations can significantly affect the properties of the matrix. Almost all of this recent work on the kinetics of aging and microstructure evolution in SiC_p/Al [3,4,6–10] has been on powder metallurgy processed composites. In particular, no comparison has been made of the aging behavior of the matrix in the composite and the control alloy as a function of aging temperature. In the present work, we examine the aging behavior of the matrix in SiC_p/Al 2014 composite made by casting route at four different aging temperatures and compare the results with the unreinforced Al 2014.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The SiC_p/Al 2014 and Al 2014 materials were obtained from Duralcan in the form of extruded bars from the cast material. The nominal and actual compositions of the matrix are given in Table I.

TABLE I. Nominal and Actual Compositions of Al 2014 and of Al 2014 Matrix (Weight %)

Element	Al	Cu	Mn	Si	Mg	Fe
Nominal Al 2014	balance	4.4	0.8	0.8	0.5	0.5
Actual Al 2014	balance	4.52	0.86	1.0	0.39	0.53
Actual Al 2014 matrix	balance	5.61	0.69	0.8	0.56	0.48

The general procedure for studying the aging characteristics consisted of a) sectioning of the specimens b) heat treatment c) metallographic preparation, and d) microhardness test.

2.1 Sample preparation For Microstructural Observation

As-received materials were sectioned for microstructural examination with a Buehler Isomet low speed diamond wafer saw. For optical and scanning electron microscopy, the samples were mechanically polished to 180, 240, 320, and 600 grit of SiC, followed by finishing with 15, 11, and 9 μm diamond paste slurry on a silk polishing cloth. Both reinforced and unreinforced materials were etched in modified Keller's reagent (15% HNO_3 , 10% HCl , 5% HF , and 70% H_2O) for microstructural examination.

Samples for transmission electron microscopy were prepared by electropolishing and ion-milling techniques. In both cases each sample was first mounted on a block with Gluco cement and then mechanically polished with 240, 320, 400 and 600 grit of SiC paper to a thickness of less than 150 μm . After preliminary grinding, they were polished with 11 and 9 μm diamond paste slurry on a silk polishing cloth. Three mm disks were punched out by Gatan model 601 ultrasonic disk cutter and were thinned down to less than 30 μm by a SBT model 515 precision dimpling instrument. The load used for dimpling was 0.1 N and each sample was first dimpled with a brass wheel to a thickness near 70 μm and from then on soft cloth made of Tex met was wrapped around the wheel to minimize sample damage due to the grinding. During ion milling, Ar ions at 5 kV were used with an ion current of 30 μA , and a sample inclination of 17° to the ion beam. Liquid nitrogen cooling trap was used during the entire ion milling process. The electropolishing was performed in a solution of 75% methanol and 25% nitric acid at 20 V and 50 mA, and -30 °C. Samples were kept inside a refrigerator to prevent natural aging at room temperature.

2.2 Heat Treatment

Aging kinetics of the reinforced and unreinforced aluminum alloy were determined to evaluate the effect of SiC on the peak aging time. Small pieces of reinforced and unreinforced material (20 of each) were cut and mechanically polished on SiC papers. The samples were annealed at 415 °C for 3 hours followed by solutionizing at 495 °C for 2 hours, water quenched, and aged isothermally at 195, 180, 165, and 150 °C for various time intervals. Differential scanning calorimeter analysis was performed in a DuPont 1090 thermal analyzer with the heating rate of 10 °C/min. All results are plotted as heat flow (mW) vs. temperature per degree Celsius.

2.3 Microhardness Test

The microhardness test on the transverse and longitudinal sections of the as received and heat treated samples were performed as a function of heat treatment. The microhardness readings were taken in the matrix of the composite alloy in the area where a few SiC particles were found. The measurements were carried out at room temperature using M-400 LECO Vickers micro hardness tester on a well polished sample. The load was 0.25 N with 20 seconds indentation time. The microhardness results were plotted against aging time, at a given temperature, to obtain the aging curve.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of the As-Received and Heat Treated Materials

The microstructure of the as-received reinforced material examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is shown in Fig. 1. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), showed Cu rich dispersoids in Al matrix. Formation of these dispersoids is due to the presence of the excess amount of Cu in the matrix (Table I). During solidification and extrusion process of the alloy, these coarse Cu-rich dispersoids tend to form at the SiC particles and in the interdendritic region of the matrix.

Figure 2 shows dislocations at the interface between the SiC particles and Al matrix in the as-received condition. During heat treatment of SiC_p/Al 2014 at 195 °C, the higher concentration of excess vacancies and dislocations are expected to provide a short circuit path for heterogeneous nucleation of S' precipitates, Fig. 3. Mahon et al. [11] have observed similar decoration of dislocations by precipitates. At 150 °C, even though the excess vacancies and dislocations are present, the aging temperature is very low and a homogeneous nucleation of the GP zones predominates. The heterogeneous nucleation at dislocations would appear not to contribute at low aging temperature. Hence the matrix in the composite and the unreinforced alloy at 150 °C would show less heterogeneous nucleation and growth of precipitates. This was confirmed by TEM. Figures 4 shows the precipitation in the matrix, aged at 150 °C. Similar precipitates were observed in the unreinforced Al 2014.

3.2 Aging Behavior

The aging characteristics (hardness vs. aging time) at different temperatures of Al 2014 and the matrix of SiC_p/Al 2014 are shown in Figs. 5 through 7. Figures 5 and 6 show the aging curves of the unreinforced Al 2014 and of the matrix at different aging temperatures. It can be seen that the time to peak age in Al 2014 matrix decreased much more with decreasing aging temperature than in the unreinforced alloy. This can be seen more clearly in Fig. 7 (a and b), where we compare the aging characteristics of the matrix and the unreinforced alloy at 195 °C and 150 °C, the extreme aging temperatures. The reinforced material reached peak hardness in about 2.5 h while the unreinforced alloy took about 9.5 h, Fig. 7a. At 150 °C, both materials peak aged around the same time, Fig. 7b.

The small shift in the time to peak age for Al 2014 (Fig. 5) and the concomitant fall in the peak hardness can be rationalized in terms of the nucleation and growth phenomena of precipitates. At 195 °C, the precipitates were smaller in number and coarser relative to those obtained at 150 °C (Figs. 3,4). The result is lower hardness in the unreinforced alloy heat treated at 195 °C, but due to higher diffusion rate, there will be an increase in the aging kinetics of the matrix. In the case of the Al matrix in the composite, the behavior is much more complex.

The difference in time to peak age (Δt) between the Al 2014 matrix and Al 2014 as function of aging temperature is shown in Fig. 8. As the aging temperature increased, the difference in peak aging time between Al 2014 matrix and the unreinforced Al 2014 became larger. Note at 150 °C the difference in peak aging time between the reinforced and the unreinforced material is rather negligible. At 195 °C this difference is about 7 hours. This means that the aging behavior of the two becomes very different as the aging temperature increases.

It is well known [12,13] that the formation of GP zone and its transition to θ'' and θ' in Al-Cu

system is only possible when the alloy is aged at a temperature below the GP zone solvus. So if, for example, the aging temperature is above the θ'' but below θ' solvus, then there will be no GP zones and the first precipitate will be θ' , heterogeneously nucleated at dislocations. One would expect a similar phenomenon to occur during heat treatment of Al-Cu-Mg alloy. At high aging temperatures, the S' precipitates nucleate heterogeneously on dislocations and grow as laths on $(210)_\alpha$ in $[001]$ directions [14]. At lower temperatures the first precipitates to nucleate are the coherent Cu-rich GP zones. It is important to mention that the nucleation of GP zones at low temperatures is mostly homogeneous and excess vacancies introduced by quenching are thought to play an important role in their formation. Upon quenching the reinforced composite, the soft matrix undergoes a plastic deformation due to the substantial thermal stresses resulting from the CTE difference between Al matrix and SiC particles. The plastic deformation of the matrix will result in a large number of dislocations and vacancies. These defects would appear to accelerate the aging kinetics of the matrix at high aging temperatures. Such effects do not seem to be effective at low aging temperatures. Differential scanning calorimetry scans confirmed this in a qualitative manner. Figure 9 (a and b) shows the DSC scans of samples peak aged at 150 and 195 °C. We note from this figure that at 150 °C, both matrix in the composite and the unreinforced Al alloy showed the presence of GP zones as well as the S' precipitates. However, at 195 °C, there was no formation of the GP zones in the matrix or the unreinforced alloy, because of the heterogeneous nucleation sites provided by dislocation and vacancies produced by quenching and/or thermal mismatch. The DSC scan monitored only S' at 195 °C. The DSC peaks for the unreinforced alloy and the matrix are somewhat shifted. This may be due to the difference in the solute distribution in the two. The kinetics of aging of the matrix, as mentioned above, were much accelerated vis a vis the unreinforced alloy because of the much higher dislocation density in the matrix.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The kinetics of aging of Al 2014 matrix were observed to depend very sensitively on the aging temperature. The reinforced material peak aged much faster than the unreinforced matrix at 195 °C. However, the difference in aging kinetics between the matrix and the unreinforced alloy was minimal at 150 °C. The relatively large difference between thermal expansion coefficients of SiC and Al resulted in substantial stresses which generated dislocations at and near the interface on quenching. During aging at 195 °C, the high density of dislocations would provide a short-circuit path for heterogeneous nucleation and fast growth of S' precipitates resulting in accelerated aging of the matrix. As the aging temperature was lowered, the difference in aging kinetics between the reinforced and the unreinforced materials diminished. This was attributed to the homogeneous nucleation of GP zones and a decrease in growth rate of precipitates at lower aging temperature. The DSC results confirmed that at lower aging temperatures both GP zones and S' precipitates existed in the Al matrix. However, at higher aging temperatures the incidence of GP zone formation decreased and at 195 °C, only S' precipitates heterogeneously nucleated on the dislocations.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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6. REFERENCES

1. R.J. Arsenault and N. Shi, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, **81** (1986) 175.

2. K.K. Chawla and M. Metzger, *J. of Mater. Sci.*, **7**, 34(1972) .
3. R.J. Arsenault and R.M. Fisher, *Scr. Met.*, **17**, 67(1983).
4. Mary Vogelsang, R.J. Arsenault, and R.M. Fisher, *Met. Trans.*, **17A**, 379(1986) .
5. S. Suresh, T. Christman, and Y. Sugimura, *Scr. Met.*, **23**, 1602(1989).
6. T. Christman and S. Suresh, *Acta Met.*, **36**, 1691(1988).
7. T.G. Nieh and R. Karlak, *Scr. Met.*, **18**, 25(1984).
8. T. Christman, A. Needleman, S. Nutt, and S. Suresh, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, **107A**, 49(1989).
9. H.J. Rack, in *Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials, Vol.2*, Elsevier Applied Science, New York, 1987, P.382.
10. J. Papazian, *Metall. Trans.*, **19A**, 2945(1988) .
11. G.J. Mahon, J.M. Howe, and A.K. Vasudevan, *Acta Met.*, **38**, 1503(1990) .
12. G.W. Lorimer, *Precipitation Processes in Solids*, The Metallurgical Society, Warrendale, 1978, p. 88.
13. D.A. Porter and K.E. Easterling, *Phase Transformation in Metals and Alloys*, Van Nos trand Reinhold Company, New York, 1981, p. 308.
14. R.N. Wilson and P.G. Partridge, *Acta Met.*, **13**, 1321(1965).

Fig. 1 SEM micrograph of the as-received SiC_p/Al 2014 composite showing (a) Cu rich dispersoids in the matrix, and (b) EDX mapping of Cu.

Fig. 2 Dislocations in the as-received SiC_p/Al 2014 composite material. TEM.

Fig. 3 TEM of SiC_p/Al 2014 heat treated at 195 °C (peak aged) showing heterogeneous nucleation of the precipitates on dislocations.

Fig. 4 TEM of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{Al 2014}$, heat treated at 150°C (peak aged). Note the homogeneous distribution of the precipitates.

Fig. 5 Variation in microhardness of the unreinforced Al 2014 as a function of aging time at different temperatures.

Fig. 6 Variation in matrix microhardness of SiCp/Al 2014 as a function of aging time at different temperatures.

Fig. 7 Comparison of aging characteristics (a) at 195 °C of the Al 2014 matrix and the unreinforced Al 2014 and (b) at 150 °C of the Al 2014 matrix and the unreinforced Al 2014.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the difference in peak aging time (Δt) as a function of temperature. Note as the aging temperature increases the difference in peak aging time between the reinforced and the unreinforced material becomes larger.

Fig. 9a DSC scans of the unreinforced Al 2014 showing the presence of GP zone and S' precipitate at 150 °C and only the presence of S' precipitates at 195 °C, and (b) showing the same thing for the Al matrix in the reinforced material.